

Critical Analysis of Dr. B R Ambedkar's Vision

Manu G.

Ph.D. Research Scholar in Management studies, IMK, Karyavattom Campus, University of Kerala, Trivandrum, India.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15504841>

ABSTRACT:

The focus of this study is intended to identify the critical analysis of Ambedkar's idea in the stimulus vision of modern concepts. The acceleration of those visions has created a common bearing of things that may polish remaining restructured questions to ask through the fundamental social opportunities, equalities, democratic conservation and representation possibility in the matter of re-union of constitutional sustainability and integrity of sovereign ruling with or without political stamina. Provided that the critical intensity has made a clear picture of responsible tact and non-responsible tact, two categorical dismantling facts already happened it may exhibit on Ambedkar's visions through the self-disciplinary actions over that were in vain at least. The paramount observation has declared that, this study has laid down various aspects and ideas but it may think overall where had no clear to upcoming intensity of common proceedings i.e., regarding the law bondage especially certain amicable amendments, summarised mismatch, priority non-selection etc, where has a detailed sample matter unfortunately may be fluctuated even though which remaining a determined rejection and also it may import a certain issue automatically created and complexities driven wherein reflect a descending order of codification documents, that may be enforced at all. Hence, this article primarily accepts the predominant issues therein taken and to controlled both as theoretical and analytical examination whether it may be sought a deem fit or not, or may be a social negligence and target compactness or whether has deem rejoined a contemplated exclusion of modern vision of the Ambedkar's perceptions, mainly in the constitutional and social representation and legal citizen rights and opportunities and its various approaches.

KEYWORDS:

responsible tact, amicable amendments, summarised mismatch,
priority non-selection, social representation.

.....

INTRODUCTION:

The prima facie vision of this study is certain objections submitted in the interpretation of Ambedkar's ideology. The major rejection in this part, says that Ambedkar basically gave a sustained doctrine of rights and responsibility of the citizen consciousness and also, he made a radical change from the orthodox human mind to the socially responsible peoples. But, in the light of this, some prohibition matters were lost there, because the orthodox human capacity of the inherent power shall be connected with social contract and it may always escalate to them as a nobility to the social scenario other than common people's needs and wants, may be sacrifice. Since, they have practised, upper, middle and lower citizens, categorically they inbuilt an unobserved caste system, wherein freely ruled behind the law, till now.

This framework of discrimination shall be strictly prohibited by law, but the law may hesitate several questions like sanctity and legal enforceability etc, But the constitution is prevailing there, overactions and beliefs are a breach of these boundaries especially the rule of law and the constitutional remedies. In these circumstances, the Ambedkar visions may be failed because the inherent orthodox power impose a certain overruling against all constitutional remedies, thus the result is that the lawful enforceability may be vanished from our society and it grave an ulterior scatter ship make and breach the lawful stabilities.

Provided that, this paper has attempted several issues that include responsible tact and non-responsible tact, amicable amend-

ments, summarised mismatch, priority non-selection, social representation and avoidance of non-participation in public forum or not fix in equitable manner.

OBJECT OF THE STUDY

The overriding objects of the study as following manner, that:

1. To identify the Equalities of Citizen in Land distribution
2. To evaluate the Wealth distribution
3. To determine Non participation in sovereign authorities
4. To interpret the Amicable Amendment
5. To insist certain tool of Reservation imbalance
6. To find out the rule of law and its Responsible tact.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The major finding of the scope of the study refers are:

- » the responsible tacts are compulsory implementing
- » The settlement of social contract should be paradigm shifts between beliefs and rights of the peoples
- » Non-responsible tact shall be flexible nature
- » To increase the social representation
- » To prohibit non-participation discrimination
- » To original constitution compulsorily rigidity maintained, no flexible manner
- » Not permit the constitution amendment, especially in cents of relevant provisions
- » Allow insert new provisions, central structure not deciding

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study has been conducted in descriptive style and to use secondary data wherein it is collected from the documentation of published journals and Articles. It is conceived as a conceptual analytical study and recommendation nature where it has admitted innovative substantial requirements of certain questions in renounc-

es nature which categorically split as responsible and non-responsible tact accordingly.

THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK REGARDING EQUAL PARTICIPATION

The conceptual framework confined herein follows as:

Figure: 01, Source: This study

The interpretation of the above said conceptual framework clearly envisages that the responsible tact and non-responsible tact, summarised mismatch, priority non-selection, social representation and avoidance of non-participation in state jurisdiction. The blue circle indicates the whole documents of the state constitution and the red line indicates the equal participation with mere advisable balance of social justice and rule of law.

Provided that, the state of the jurisdiction embodied a secure constitution of the state which confined the strict and flexible bundle of laws practice and enforced. But, herein say that, the constitution document is presently prevailed and it has certain tact's to play the state, it is known as Responsible tact's, and further non-responsible tact's as another form which handled the bulk of beliefs, its conversations and inherent rights, it always says that the precedent, this kind of propaganda is also known as non-responsible

tact's.

This framework has shown that the breach of laws between responsible and non-responsible tact, and combat each other. The result is confined the equal participation is entirely vain, deciding obiter dicta of this frame of rule of law, it may be beyond the state of jurisdiction.

ANALYSE OF RECTIFICATION SENARIO:

The rectification scenario reflects the present condition of the discrimination bars between two groups, which confined the orthodox humanities and scattered humanities. The precedent traditional humanities consider a mere certain abstractive privilege, it is not a reality outcome; it will impose others automatically; therefore, they have breached all existing laws and lawful justice. But whereas the scattered humanities have practiced scattered type, no amalgamation or organised peoples. They have automatically dismantled each other. Therefore, they have socially backward and to beg all human needs and wants in lawful jurisdiction of the state, vice versa. The major tools of rectification scenarios are; Equalities of Citizen in Land distribution, Wealth distribution, non-participation in sovereign authority, Amicable Amendment, Reservation imbalance and the rule of law and its Responsible tact. However, the responsible tact's indicate higher rates in the state, they maintain a peaceful life and get recognition of citizens without discrimination, and also the rule of law is absolutely bound to implement and reduce the non-responsible tact's. But, in the case of non-responsible tact's which show an increase the state will go down in the inherent mechanism, which leads to the bottom through incapacity to move responsible tact's or bearing social justice needs and wants of the citizen. It obstructs all the rights of states, it may overrule state policy and proceedings, it may be a harmful injury sustained by the state ju-

risdiction of sovereignty. Hence, only the benevolent state rule of law, assured to accord towards the responsible tact's, and it endeavours to pursue the follow of the constitution security and social decency and dignity of the citizen welfare osculation, in various corners.

However, the various components of responsible tact's hereby devolved as follows:

I. Equalities of Citizen in Land Distribution:

The constitution spoke out the equalities, but still the equal frame of work is the impossible manner. Because all kinds of articles or properties may be separate from the common people, even though the modern state has faced a lot of issues we could see in the daily news at all. Prima facie, the state properties are categorically split and divided into all citizens for run or maintaining their wellbeing life. It shall be separated into personal, industrial and state parts. The citizen share has equalised according to certain laws and as per distributed properties in minimum bear of size for the residential and agricultural needs. In the second scenario, the industrial part, which seeks industrial innovations or infrastructure development in the mechanical inventions to use this division, therein both private and Governmental service to engage this work or separately dealing it. Thirdly, the state properties, it has free to opt state and to use state intervention, the business improvement and relation build up between foreign countries. Unfortunately, we can't see that the state properties have no division incurred in an equalised manner even the democracy ruling of law, sustaining at present. It deserves to all people, "equal land and equal life", which are inherent rights of all citizens, it should get due to the birth of the state and birth of the people within the state. It envisages that there is nothing to rule in lands of law and no clear picture has been insisted in the

constitution wherein all kinds of land equal distribution may be lost of this part under the Ambedkar visions. Similarly, Dr. Ambedkar's vision of social justice emanates from his quest for a just society, which is based on the idea of casteless society.

II. Wealth Distribution:

In the present scenario, we sought the uttermost richest peoples living here, but simultaneously in the opposite part has created poor people's accordingly. Its parameter concerned that they have not maintained any sufficient land, house, clothes, food etc, therefore different lifestyles wherein moved unless they have no recognised people in the country. So, the distribution of wealth means a minimum level of sustainable wealth insisted towards the mass peoples. But in reality, it says that all people are afraid to attend to this means of wealth preparation. On the other hand, the mass wealth has accumulated in some limited wealthy people's hands. Therefore, the parameter of wealth circulation surely controlled the wealth inflow and outflow which required the mandatory determination of wealth instruments. The wealth distribution mainly focuses on the distribution mechanism, which means that the state has power to move the inflow and outflow of wealth transformation, which consist of a minimum equalities input on it in the minimum decency. But we could see there was no nothing parameter prevailed as none of this. In effect the wealth has accumulated in certain minority hands as called richest people and none of wealth is not accumulated in certain groups, called poorest people. This kind of two different peoples has created and they will control the overall wealth distribution of inflow and outflow in the state. Hence, this type of hypocrisy slightly performed in the state behaviour, the result is that the major portion of peoples has not attained any welfare upliftment till now. It may be removed and grave a suitable wealth distribution towards the people but this wealth distribution provi-

sions have not been read out within the constitution; it may be avoided by the Ambedkar vision of statements.

III. Non-Participation in Sovereign Authorities:

It also consented to the idea of participation of all kinds of groups of peoples in the sovereign authority. It means that the proportionate representation shall be fixed and given a mere chance to all groups, not certain classes. Hence, the participation of representation, particularly the vulnerable groups may be excluded in this scenario. The after effect, the said peoples have day to day throw the street. Because, they have not given their needs and wants in the public forum. They are categorically separated from the ultimate welfare in the society. Therefore, it will take strictly to participate in all kinds of peoples without any discrimination which deal with the employment, opportunities, jobs, and demand for proclamation platforms etc, wherever not accommodating any participation rule may be practiced, the result is that one group of vulnerable communities may be highly backward in our society. However, in the present rule and acts not covering this idea of participation which minimum standard of equality has been not practised anywhere in our society at all. But it is very harmful behaviour of the developing society. No where it has discussed the modern concept of Ambedkar ideology in the social revolution.

IV. Amicable Amendment:

This idea, which follows the constitutional amendment portion, means that the international recognition and standards kept in particular amendment is very need full and use the transformation tools for social innovation of development criteria. But it has particularly two groups, rigid and flexible. Our constitution has involved both of two mechanisms adopted. But sometimes it may arise certain questions before the interpretation of these parameter

declarations, that strictly we say that some provisions surely adopt the rigid character, shall be not amended at all. On the other hand, some provisions may be amended which fall under the flexible manner. Hence, hereby say that it must follow the rigid character in charge of fundamental rights, directive principles and vulnerable communities' clause etc, shall be fixed in rigidity. Further the remaining portions shall follow the flexible interpretation, no doubt in these circumstances. But the main argument is that the amendments are very high paced rather than comparatively other states. It may always affect the interpretation of Ambedkar democratic vision.

V. Reservation Imbalance:

It is mainly focused on the reservation concept, wherein the reservation is a very urgent need, but its components are not freely working towards the reserved communities. The main reason is that there is no strict law found to distribute the grants funds or reservation rotation etc, among the reserved category for their welfare, it is said to be one problem facing the reservation mechanism. On the other hand, the reservation imbalance. It implies that the reservation is not an equal manner, especially the distribution mainly categorised as a group which is either majority or minority, where it has not followed any equal parameter at all. Therefore, the suggestion is that the reservation must be divided in an equal formula and prioritised groups may boost their reservation in the matter of employment, education and economic capabilities. Otherwise, they can't move forward and not attain welfare life accomplishment. Similarly, the state has given industries to the poorest reserved families through which they will attain a good life and hence all the marginalized people may have earned a standard life in the upcoming future. Hence this part also some imbalance incurred it therefore we can analyse this may be slightly affected by Ambedkar philosophical dismantling approach at all.

VI. The Rule of Law and its Responsible Tact:

It is a subject which renders the rule of law and its responsible tact. The rule of responsible tact is a primary object to urgent needs of social equalization in the crystal division of people's needs and emergency life sustainability. It means that the rule of the law should be practiced and implemented through responsible tact, which deals with the responsible creation of citizens without any violation of exploitation, harassment and apprehension. But at present which exhibit a high volume of crime, violation, exploitation, humiliation and atrocities practised against the human body and their life destruction activities, which were practiced without any fear. Therefore, these kinds of problems increase in daily life within the state. Provided that, the rule of responsible tact has created a responsible society and made responsible citizens under rule by law, anyone who may breach it knowingly or unknowingly, the result which has imposed certain lawful rules and provisions where who has been punished under prevailing Acts accordingly. In nutshell, responsible tact implies a responsible rule of law of the land.

VII. Democratic Opinion:

It is generally to find out that democracy is a centric rule of authority, which is like a federation system in the modern concept of democratic vision according to Ambedkar's thoughts and his framework. Democracy is a system which has intended to create a government through the vote by selection and representation of sovereignty from the public majority decision. But many problems herein subsist that politics, groups, favouritism and nepotism, majority apprehension and loyal dignity etc. which harmful and obstruction make suitable democratic functions. Hence, suggestion is that if categorically divide in the centric power and pursue the representation of ruling wherein allow all peoples without political influence and their apprehension at all. Unfortunately, the Ambed-

kar idea does not touch on this area, the result is that a heavy loss to the political gap may be created and the political influence is one of the major apprehensions of Democratic smooth functions and its working towards the rule of laws to the society thereof.

CONCLUSION:

This study is a mere critical perception of interpretation in Dr. Ambedkar's vision and his ideas. But meanwhile Dr. Ambedkar was not only the architect of the Indian Constitution; he was concentrated in the field of freedom fighter, philosopher, thinker, writer, economist, editor, and a prophet for Buddhism in India. In conclusion, it's a critical inherent attempt of research that gives analytical intrinsic values into the ideology and views of Dr. Ambedkar, especially in the field of Equalities of Citizen in Land distribution, Wealth distribution, non-participation in sovereign authorities, Amicable Amendment, Reservation imbalance and Rule of law and its responsible tact. Hence, herein a suitable renovation framework is an urgent requirement and dismantling certain social contract with sovereign authorities. This blueprint is a golden star of modern democracy and to attain a sustainable development by accomplishment of the people's dignity and status, otherwise it is vain.

References:

1. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353717272_The_Vision_of_Dr_Babasaheb_Ambedkar_on_Various_Issues
2. <https://rjpn.org/ijcspub/viewpaperforall.php?paper=IJCSP13A1008>

Funding:

This study was not funded by any grant.

Conflict of interest:

The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

About the License:

© The Authors 2024. The text of this article is open access and licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.